

HYMES AND CHOMSKY'S CONTRIBUTIONS IN THE DEVELOPMENT
OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE IN SECOND LANGUAGE
TEACHING AND LEARNING

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***Abstract.** The term communicative competence captures the notion that the ability to use language in interaction requires not just control of linguistic form but also awareness of rules of use in different contexts (Hymes, 1972). Communicative competence is a slippery term: different actors in second language (L2) research, education, and assessment interpret the term in a variety of ways and use it for a range of purposes, perhaps particularly in the field of languages for specific purposes (LSP). This is unfortunate because it is a key concept in LSP, as in applied linguistics more generally.*

***Keywords.** Language For Specific Purposes (LSP), Communicative Competence, Language Education, Second Language (L2) Research, Second And Foreign Language Teaching*

Introduction. Communicative competence (Hymes, 1972) is one of the most important notions in languages for specific purposes (LSP) teaching and learning. Many key texts in LSP focus on language user's abilities to communicate effectively, or simply 'get things done' in particular contexts of communication. LSP is related to "the communicative needs of speakers of a second language in facing a particular workplace, academic, or professional context" (Basturkmen & Elder, 2004, p. 672), and these needs include "not only linguistic knowledge but also background knowledge relevant to the communicative context in which learners need to operate" (Douglas, 2013, p. 371). English for Specific Purposes

(ESP) focuses on “the demands placed by academic or workplace contexts on communicative behaviours” (Hyland, 2002, p. 386) and “the language, skills, and genres appropriate to the specific activities the learners need to carry out in English” (Johns, 2013, p. 2). The importance of contexts and goals for communication is clear, creating a natural connection between LSP and the notion of communicative competence.

Yet as the notion has evolved over time, different subfields of applied linguistics like second language (L2) research, teaching, and testing have pursued divergent interpretations, creating contradictions for LSP, which has traditionally drawn on these subfields. This paper re-examines communicative competence from these three perspectives to highlight tensions between theory and practice in LSP and propose a revised model which constitutes a more faithful representation of Hymes’ original notion and is also closer to current concerns in LSP assessment.

Main part

The origins of the term communicative competence

This concept was first proposed by Hymes (1972) in an essay where the sociolinguist argued for a linguistic theory which could focus on “the capacities of persons, the organisation of verbal means for socially defined purposes, and the sensitivity of rules to situations” (p. 292). Hymes was reacting to Chomsky’s famous distinction between the competence of “an ideal speaker-listener, in a completely homogeneous speech community, who knows its language perfectly,” on one hand, and “errors (random or characteristic) in applying his knowledge of the language in actual performance,” on the other (Chomsky, 1965, p. 3). Hymes (1972) recognised this distinction as a contemporary interpretation of a tradition leading back to Saussure and even Humboldt, and questioned the prioritisation of linguistic competence, that is, “tacit knowledge of language structure” (p. 271) over performance, or “imperfect manifestation of underlying system” (p. 272).

Hymes saw the restrictive view taken by Chomsky’s linguistic theory as “almost a declaration of irrelevance” of sociolinguistics (p. 270), and one which “omits almost everything of sociocultural significance” (p. 280).

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For Hymes, communicative competence thus includes speakers' knowledge of linguistic and sociolinguistic rules as well as their ability to use this knowledge in interaction. It is distinct from actual language use in interaction, which depends not only on speakers but also their interlocutors and unfolding events, and comes under the heading of performance. This view thus calls into question Chomsky's competence/performance distinction between linguistic knowledge and language use.

Conclusion. Both D.Hymes and N.Chomsky have a profound influence on the development of communicative competence in second language teaching and learning. Whilst Chomsky's introduction of the concepts of linguistic competence and performance laid the theoretical framework for understanding the innate knowledge of language systems, Hymes' extension to include sociolinguistic and pragmatic dimensions underlined the importance of using language pertinently in social contexts. Their associated contributions have led to a more extensive and effective approach to language education, integrating grammatical knowledge with real-life communicative skills.

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